

Geroscience and inflammaging in the era of the COVID-19 pandemic

MD Anisleidys Martinez Infante¹, MD William Quintero Pérez¹, MD Alexander Ariel Padrón-González²

¹ Faculty of Medical Sciences, “Dr Miguel Enriquez”, Ramon Pinto No. 202, Luyanó, Diez de Octubre, Havana Medical Sciences University, AP 10049, 11000 CP, Havana City, Cuba

² Central Laboratory of Cerebrospinal Fluid (LABCEL). , Ramon Pinto No. 202, Luyanó, Diez de Octubre, Havana Medical Sciences University, AP 10049, 11000 CP, Havana City, Cuba

Corresponding author: Alexander Ariel Padrón-González, Faculty of Medical Sciences, “Dr Miguel Enriquez”, Central Laboratory of Cerebrospinal Fluid (LABCEL), Ramon Pinto No. 202, Luyanó, Diez de Octubre, Havana Medical Sciences University, AP 10049, 11000 CP, Havana City, Cuba

Email: alexpadronglez@gmail.com

Introduction

Aging encompasses numerous biological changes and declines of function. Aging is currently considered a major risk factor for cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases. In fact, worldwide extended lifespan creates a new challenge for health systems. Geroscience is an interdisciplinary field that aims to understand the complex and multidirectional relationships between the biology of aging and age-related diseases. The geroscience hypothesis posits that addressing aging will prevent and delay the emergence or severity of multiple chronic diseases and other conditions such as frailty, fatigability and chronic pain. (1)

Geroscience and aging biology

Genomic instability, telomere attrition, epigenetic alterations, loss of proteostasis, deregulated nutrient sensing, mitochondrial dysfunction, cellular senescence, stem cell exhaustion, and altered intercellular communication have been defined as the hallmarks of aging. All these molecular pathways and cellular processes are influenced by environmental and genetic factors. Currently, the GenAge database lists over 300 human aging-related genes, with small or moderate effects on longevity phenotype. (2,3)

Recent advances in molecular and genetic studies suggest heritability of human longevity genes and their implications in morbidity and mortality rates. In older people the genetic component becomes increasingly important, influencing to a variable extent many common polygenic conditions (hypertension, coronary heart disease, and diabetes) that ramp up from middle-age onwards and influence lifespan determination. We can not modify our heritability genome, but gene expression is influenced by the epigenome (chemical modifications to genes and associated proteins). (3)

Traditional approaches of targeting individual diseases one at a time is not enough to impact human longevity. There is presently an increasing interest (and major investment by entrepreneurs), in developing compounds capable of affecting the epigenome in beneficial ways to slow, and even reverse, the biology of aging. Clinical data indicates that geroprotective drugs that target hallmarks of aging, such as

rapamycin and metformin, may be effective at delaying or reversing age-related disease and improving healthy lifespan. (3)

Currently the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) does not recognize aging as a disease or indication. For that reason it is difficult to develop and apply translational geroscience interventions or to obtain approval by regulatory agencies to target the aging process itself. Besides, until now, the clinical trials that have been carried out in geroscience have the limitation of following traditional methods.(4)

Immunosenescence and Inflammaging

In aging, immunosenescence occurs mainly due to thymic involution, chronic antigenic stimulation (history of the individual exposure to pathogens), and replicative senescence. The hallmarks of immunosenescence include: reduced capacity to respond to new antigens, the accumulation of memory T cells and a low-grade inflammation termed inflammaging. Cellular markers with a predominance of memory T lymphocytes and natural killers are altered, which leads to a predominance of low-grade inflammation and its associated diseases such as autoimmunity, atherosclerosis, cardiovascular diseases, dementia, cancer. (5,6)

Inflammaging is related to an increase in several proinflammatory molecules like cytokines, chemokines, miRNAs, and all these mediators can develop senescence associated phenotype. This status reflects the ability of each person to keep the immune homeostasis against internal and external challenges and explain wide variances in biological inflammatory age related to chronological age. (7,8)

Geroscience and COVID-19 pandemic

In the era of the COVID-19 pandemic it is clear that older adults are most vulnerable to hospitalization, pneumonia, disability and death following infection with SARS-CoV-2 virus. In fact elderly are at much higher risk for developing pneumonia than younger individuals, and one of the reasons is that elderly people have a ciliary and flagellar dysfunction : the lung's first line of defense. There is sufficient experimental evidence to confirm that SARS-CoV-2 infection produces states of ciliary and flagellar dysfunction. Recently, Bermejo and collaborators evaluated the pulmonary and extrapulmonary pathogenesis of COVID-19 from the point of view of ciliary dysfunction. (9,10)

Coronaviruses are also neuroinvasive, neurotropic, cause necroptosis and release of damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMP). These pro-inflammatory mechanisms establish a redundant and amplifying cycle with the production of molecules such as chemokines and cytokines that exacerbate the inflammatory and neurodegenerative process. Then addressing degenerative aging processes therapeutically appears promising to increase the resiliency and homeostasis of individuals in COVID-19 situations as well as promoting greater public health stability during future pandemics. (11,12)

Interestingly, it has been reported that there are centenarians showing remarkable capacity to recover after SARS-CoV-2 infection. These experiences could help in identifying protective biological mechanisms underlying the coronavirus infection and understanding the mechanisms that regulate aging and age-related diseases. Older persons have heterogeneous health status resulting from the interactions between their individual longevity genes and environmental factors. Also they have an exclusive signature: an extraordinary capacity and ability to live with different diseases, delaying disability and death for even some decades. (13)

Pertinent questions come about considering this discussion. So, what can be done now to empower general population, health and wellness professionals with longevity medicine as well as geroscience? What about the status of geroscience in health policies?

The concepts of geroscience and longevity sciences have long been understood both by scientists and the general public; however, the recognition in medical spheres has been slow due to the preconceived idea that we can not modify aging. We are now doing aging biology, but not geroscience. It is true that we can not change the aging process related to chronological age, but we can modify lifespan and healthspan with simple interventions in behavioral changes. Although geroscience mentions in PubMed are rare, the rate of increase (only 4 in 2014 and 65 as of November 2021) shows a progressive change in the perceptions and acceptance of this field. (1)

In geroscience, there is a growing worldwide need for accessible high-quality educational tools, contemporary concepts, theoretical frameworks and cutting-edge advances in longevity medicine. New models of clinical trials with potential geroprotective therapies and their possible combinations are needed to enable

extensive data collection and analysis of their potential benefits and indications. Public health policies are vital to foster prevention in personalized lifestyle medicine, addressing a patient's health with the information needed to keep control of their health.

Precision of longevity therapies should be individualized, considering each patient's specific genes, environment, lifestyle, early life factors, psychosocial, epidemiological and socioeconomic patterns of risk factors to avoid the impacts on health in later age. Targeting the expression of longevity genes can avoid multiple diseases and may also have critical implications for healthcare and social policies, both during the current crisis and planning for future emergencies. Increasing open access and involving public and professional health practitioners in geroscience education is essential as well as developing a robust international network.

So, what may come next? The rationales discussed suggest new regulatory and institutional commitments to enable the forward movement in development of the science in longevity medicine and technologies.

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